

MICROSTRUCTURE AND INTERFACIAL CONTROL IN COMPOSITES OF PYREX GLASS
AND CALCIUM ALUMINOSILICATE GLASS-CERAMIC REINFORCED WITH NICALON
OR CARBON FIBRES.

S M Bleay and V D Scott
School of Materials Science
University of Bath, UK.

ABSTRACT

Detailed microstructural studies on several composite systems based either on a Pyrex glass matrix or calcium aluminosilicate are described. Fibre reinforcements involve Nicalon and carbon, whilst fabrication has employed the hot-pressing route. The use of analytical transmission electron microscopy on thin sections prepared from bulk composites has revealed significant differences in the microstructure of the fibre/matrix interface, such as carbon segregation and sodium diffusion. Parallel studies have been carried out to assess mechanical behaviour of the different composites, including the use of an indentation method to evaluate bond strength at the interface. The data have shown that interface microstructure may be related to the strength of the interfacial bond and, in particular, the fracture toughness of the composite via the degree of fibre pullout from the matrix.

KEYWORDS: Composites; matrix, glass; interface; fibre, ceramic/graphite.

1. INTRODUCTION

Glass and glass-ceramic matrix composites reinforced with ceramic fibres have several potentially attractive properties, including high specific stiffness and strength, good corrosion and abrasion resistance, and retention of these properties to high temperature. As a consequence, much research and development has been carried out on these materials over the last twenty years with a view to their use in chemical plant and in aerospace applications (1,2,3,4). The object of incorporating fibres into glass and glass-ceramic is, essentially, to change the failure mode from the catastrophic brittle type characteristic of the unreinforced matrix to the controlled failure mechanism associated with energy absorbing processes such as interface debonding and fibre pullout in the composite. Obviously, the nature of the interface will play a significant role in the type of fracture; for example, if the interfacial

bond is too strong, cracks will propagate into the fibre from the matrix and an undesirable brittle fracture occurs, whereas if the interfacial bond is too weak, then insufficient energy will be absorbed in fracture and delamination and buckling may arise. Hence the need to produce composites with interfaces optimised to meet specific material requirements.

This paper focuses attention on microstructural studies of three composite systems; Pyrex glass reinforced with Hercules HM carbon fibres, Pyrex glass reinforced with Nicalon fibres, and calcium aluminosilicate glass-ceramic (CAS) reinforced with Nicalon fibres. Parallel studies are made of the interfacial friction stress of the composites using a micro-indentation technique and experiments on some heat-treated specimens are also carried out, the overall objective being to relate interface microstructure with micromechanics and, in turn, with the thermal history of the composite.

2. EXPERIMENTAL

Specimens were cut from bulk composite using a resin-bonded diamond saw at low speed and sections prepared by grinding on a diamond wheel followed by polishing on Buehler Metlap discs, with diamond slurries of, progressively, 9 μ m, 6 μ m and 1 μ m particle size. The interfacial friction stress between fibre and matrix was measured using a micro-indentation technique as follows (5).

A Vickers pyramidal microhardness indenter was applied to the centre of a fibre so that the interfacial bond was broken and the fibre depressed below the surface of the matrix. Loads were selected to produce an indentation extending from the fibre into the adjacent matrix and the interfacial friction stress, τ , was then calculated from the expression

$$\tau = F^2/4\pi^2 u R^3 E_f$$

where R is fibre radius, E_f is fibre modulus (200GPa for Nicalon, 380GPa for carbon), F is the force applied to the fibre and u the fibre depression at maximum load. F and u were calculated from measurements of indent geometry and fibre hardness.

Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) was used to examine polished sections of composite, sections of composite etched in 5% HF for 2.5 hours, and fracture surfaces of specimens broken in three-point flexure. In each case a thin layer of gold was sputtered onto the sample to prevent it charging up while under the electron beam. Compositional analysis was carried out by means of an energy-dispersive x-ray spectrometer (EDS) attached to the SEM.

Thin sections for transmission electron microscopy (TEM) were prepared from bulk material by drilling 3mm diameter discs with a hollow drill and mechanically grinding them to ~ 300 μ m thickness. The discs were then dimpled on both sides in a VCR Model D500 to leave a central thickness of ~ 20 μ m, and thinned by argon ion bombardment in a Gatan Duomill at 5kV, using a 15 $^\circ$ incidence angle until perforation of the specimen occurred and a 8 $^\circ$ incidence angle to extend the thinned area. A 200keV electron microscope fitted with an EDS system was used for most of this work.

Specimens of Nicalon/CAS composite were examined after heating in air for 60 hours at 600°C, 800°C, 1000°C and 1200°C followed by air cooling.

3. RESULTS

3.1 Pyrex glass reinforced with carbon-fibres. SEM of a polished and etched section, Fig. 1a, revealed that the Pyrex matrix contained ~ 10 vol.% of second-phase particles. EDS combined with TEM analysis showed that they consisted of glass surrounded by a thin layer of carbon. In addition, a small amount (~ 1 vol.%) of cristobalite, a polymorph of silica was found.

A TEM micrograph taken from the fibre/matrix interface region, Fig. 1b, showed the presence of a more electron transparent zone, ~ 100 nm thick, with a texture intermediate between that of the fibre and the matrix. EDS analysis showed the carbon fibre (F) to contain traces of sodium from the manufacturing process, Fig. 1c. The matrix (M) consisted of silicon, aluminium and oxygen in the proportions expected in Pyrex glass but there was some depletion in the sodium level, Fig. 1d. The interface (I) contained silicon, oxygen, sodium and carbon, Fig. 1e.

Values of interfacial shear stress (τ) recorded in the micro-indentation test are given in Table 1. An exact measure of τ was difficult to obtain with carbon fibres because relaxation effects erased the indent. However, it was evident that once sufficient force had been applied to break the interfacial bond, the fibre slid comparatively easily within the matrix under minimal load. For the calculation, an indent with 1 μ m diagonals was assumed, giving a calculated shear stress of ~ 0.01 MPa.

The fracture surface of samples subjected to a three-point bend test showed appreciable fibre pull out, equivalent to some 10 fibre diameters, to leave smooth fibre surfaces and sockets in the matrix, Fig. 1f.

3.2 Pyrex glass reinforced with Nicalon fibres. This composite material was found to contain ~ 10 vol.% of cristobalite in the matrix, Fig. 2a, numerous microcracks being observed in the neighbourhood of the cristobalite particles.

A TEM picture of the Nicalon/Pyrex interface is illustrated in Fig. 2b. The fibre (F) was found using EDS to contain silicon, carbon sodium and oxygen, Fig.2c, as reported previously for Nicalon fibres(6). An interfacial zone, ~ 50nm wide, was clearly visible and shown to contain silicon, oxygen, carbon and sodium, Fig. 2d, the oxygen and carbon levels being somewhat higher than in the interior of the fibre. The adjacent matrix region (M) was depleted in sodium compared with the glass composition, the EDS trace being similar to that shown in Fig. 1d from the Pyrex which had been reinforced with carbon fibres.

The interfacial shear strength, as measured in the micro-indentation experiment, was 4.1 ± 1.0 MPa, the loads required to initiate fibre sliding causing some damage to the matrix.

Fracture surfaces of specimens subjected to three-point bend testing showed appreciable fibre pull-out, approaching lengths of several 100 μ m and leaving smooth fibre surfaces and sockets in the matrix, Fig. 2e.

3.3 Calcium aluminosilicate reinforced with Nicalon fibres The matrix was found, using x-ray diffraction, to be mainly anorthite, $\text{CaAl}_2\text{Si}_2\text{O}_8$. Some particles a few μ m in size and amounting to no more than ~1 vol.%, (P in Fig.3a) were identified as α - Al_2O_3 by means of EDS in the SEM and selected area diffraction (SAD) in the TEM.

The microstructure of the fibre/matrix interface region showed evidence of a pronounced reaction, with a ~ 50nm wide zone (I) being formed between fibre (F) and matrix (M), Fig. 3b. EDS analysis of the fibre gave the same result as found with Nicalon in Pyrex (see Fig. 2b), whilst the matrix EDS spectrum, Fig. 3c, was consistent with the CAS structure. The interface zone (I) was found to contain elements from both the matrix and fibre, Fig. 3d, but the carbon level appeared appreciably higher than that recorded in the fibre.

After heating in air at 800 $^\circ$ C for 60h, voids were observed at the fibre/matrix interface in regions of the specimen close to the surface, Fig.4. Void formation became more extensive, the higher the temperature and, after 60h at 1200 $^\circ$ C, the type of interface illustrated in Fig. 5a was obtained. The reaction zone was now ~ 100nm wide, contained voids and consisted mostly of silicon and oxygen, Fig. 5b. The concentration of the matrix elements calcium and aluminium was much reduced and carbon was not detectable. Elsewhere in this material the fibre and matrix compositions were little different from those found in the as received composite, see Figs. 2c and 3c respectively.

Values of 3.1 ± 0.4 MPa for the interfacial friction stress were obtained for as-received material and, as heat treatments progressively changed the fibre/matrix interface structure, so they changed the interfacial friction stress. As with the microstructure, the changes were more severe in surface regions of the composite specimen. For example, values recorded in the interior of the sample after 60h at 1200 $^\circ$ C were ~ 3.1 ± 0.5 MPa but in some surface regions they were estimated to be in excess of 25 MPa.

The fracture behaviour of this composite material showed marked changes as a result of heat treatment. Failure of as-received specimens was characterised by fairly extensive fibre pullout, up to 100 μ m in length but, in heat-treated material, brittle fracture occurred producing an extensive planar surface. Fig. 5c shows fibre pullout in the relatively unaffected interior of the composite plate and brittle fracture in surface regions where the interface had been altered by heat treatment.

4. DISCUSSION

As we shall show, the behaviour of all three composite materials was dominated by the nature of the interface but, before proceeding with the argument, some comment concerning the respective matrices is required.

None of the matrices was single-phased. The presence of some cristobalite was a characteristic of both composites with Pyrex matrices, more of this phase being discovered in the Nicalon reinforced system. The different amounts of cristobalite were a consequence of different composite processing temperatures, carbon/Pyrex being hot pressed between 1100°C and 1200°C and Nicalon/Pyrex between 900°C and 1000°C. Since ~ 950°C has been shown (7) to be in the optimum recrystallisation region for Pyrex glass, it is not surprising to find there is a greater likelihood of cristobalite being formed during manufacture of the Nicalon-containing material. Indeed, even larger amounts than 10 vol.% have been discovered on occasions in Pyrex-based systems (6), with premature failure via matrix disintegration caused by the microcracking developed as a result of thermal mismatch between Pyrex and cristobalite. The 10 vol.% level of cristobalite found here appeared, however, not to produce these mechanical defects to a serious degree. With regard to the carbon-rich particles found in the carbon/Pyrex composite, these were attributed to incomplete burn-off of the organic resins used in manufacture and it was perhaps unexpected to find them in this Pyrex-based composite and not in the other. Nevertheless, the carbon-rich particles appeared to have little effect on composite properties. The occurrence of a matrix second phase in the Nicalon/CAS composite may be explained by reference to the CaO-Al₂O₃-SiO₂ phase diagram, Fig.6, where slight compositional variations in localised regions may have favoured the formation of alumina rather than aluminosilicate. Again this second phase had no discernable effect on composite properties.

Returning to the question of the fibre/matrix interface, there does appear to be some common factor in all three composite systems, namely the degree to which carbon is present in the interface regions.

In the carbon/Pyrex composite, a zone ~ 100nm wide between fibre and matrix was located which, based upon present evidence(8), was silicon oxycarbide containing some sodium diffused in from the matrix. The layer appeared to be well bonded, both to fibre and to matrix, to give a fairly good interlaminar shear strength of 39MPa (9). Once, however, the interfacial bond had been broken, the fibre was able to slide easily within the matrix, as evidenced by the measured interfacial friction stress of ~ 0.01 MPa and the extent of fibre pullout produced when mechanically testing the composite. This very low value of sliding friction is considered to be associated with the sliding of highly oriented graphite planes over one another in the outer layers of fibre.

In the Nicalon/Pyrex composite the interface was different and evidence was found of a carbon-forming reaction, as reported by Cooper and Chyung (4):

The carbon layer was only ~ 5nm thick and the main feature of the interface was the oxygen-enriched band in the outer 50nm of the fibre into which sodium had diffused to leave the adjacent matrix depleted in this element. The interfacial friction stress was substantially higher than that recorded in the carbon/Pyrex composite, at 4.1 ± 1.0 MPa, but the fibre was still able to slide sufficiently to give clean fibre pullout of some 100µm in length.

Turning to the Nicalon/CAS composite, a carbon-rich layer had formed at the fibre/matrix interface during manufacture, as in the reaction given above, but in this system it was much thicker (~ 50nm) than in Nicalon/Pyrex. This accorded with the somewhat lower values of interfacial friction stress which were recorded, 3.1 ± 0.4 MPa.

The experiments carried out on heat-treated Nicalon/CAS composite confirmed these views. Heating in air caused oxidation of the carbon-rich interfacial layer according to

and the gas produced either dispersed or formed voids. Also silicon carbide in the Nicalon fibre would be oxidised to give

and leave silica bridging the fibre and the matrix. This silica bridge produced strong bonding between the two components, as demonstrated by high interface friction stress values, in excess of 25 MPa in some cases. (The voids which occur here clearly do not act as sources of weakness). Thus the strong fibre/matrix bond allowed no significant fibre pullout and a brittle fracture mode was the inevitable result.

In summary then, the carbon layer at the fibre/matrix interface was desirable as regards mechanical properties since it allowed fibre pullout and reduced brittleness, but it provided a source of composite instability in an oxidising environment.

5. ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

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6. REFERENCES

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TABLE 1.

Composite Specimen	τ /MPa	
	Interior	Edge
Carbon/Pyrex	~ 0.01	-
Nicalon/Pyrex	4.9 ± 1.1	-
Nicalon/CAS (As-received)	3.1 ± 0.4	-
Nicalon/CAS (600°C HT)	2.9 ± 0.7	3.4 ± 1.5
Nicalon/CAS (800°C HT)	2.5 ± 0.5	3.1 ± 0.7
Nicalon/CAS (1000°C HT)	2.8 ± 0.5	3.6 ± 1.1
Nicalon/CAS (1200°C HT)	3.1 ± 0.5	$5.1 \pm 2.1^*$

* upper limit not calculable.

FIGURE 1. Carbon/Pyrex composite.

(a) deeply etched section, SEM. (b) interface region in thin foil, TEM.

(c) EDS of fibre (F).

(d) EDS of matrix (M).

(e) EDS of interface (I).

(f) fracture surface, SEM.

FIGURE 2. Nicalon/Pyrex composite.

(a) polished transverse section, SEM.

(b) interface region in thin foil, TEM.

(c) EDS of fibre (F).

(d) EDS of interface (I).

(e) fracture surface SEM.

FIGURE 3. Nicalon/CAS composite.

- (a) polished transverse section, SEM. (b) interface region in thin foil, TEM.

(c) EDS of matrix (M).

(d) EDS of interface (I).

FIGURE 4. Nicalon/CAS composite, heat treated at 800°C; interface region in thin foil, TEM.

FIGURE 5. Nicalon/CAS composite, heat treated at 1200°C;
 (a) interface region in thin foil, TEM. (b) EDS of interface.

(c) fracture surface, SEM.

FIGURE 6. CaO-Al₂O₃-SiO₂ ternary phase diagram;
 X represents stoichiometric anorthite composition.